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CALCULATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF A DEVICE FOR AUTOMATIC GAIN SELECTION OF A MEASURING AMPLIFIER

***Annotation.** The article discusses the development of a device for automatic selection of the gain of the measuring amplifier. A block diagram of a differentiator with reversible counters and an adder is presented. The main methods for constructing devices for data collection with an extended range are given. It is shown that to select the optimal structure of specialized digital computing devices, the criteria of "relationship type" and "weighted sum type" are used. It is noted that in order to evaluate the efficiency and select the optimal structure of a computational analog-to-digital converter, the criterion of the "type of relationship" is usually used, as well as information criteria for evaluating the effectiveness of communication systems - information transfer rate and throughput. It is indicated that in order to*

assess the multimode when determining the efficiency of a device, such characteristics as "equivalent relative complexity" and "equivalent efficiency" are introduced. It is recommended to use an amplifier with autoscaling when building an optimal analog-to-digital converter.

Key words: Measuring amplifier, amplification factor, analog-to-digital converter.

The intensive development of microprocessor technology has led to the creation of high-performance personal computers that make it possible to realize the significant potential of digital processing of analog information. For pairing a personal computer with research objects, data collection devices are used, the signals at the inputs of which can in many cases change in a wide (80 dB or more) dynamic range,

Fig. 1. Structural diagram of the differentiator:

RC1, RC2 - reversible counters;

SM – totalizer

the processing of such signals is necessary, in particular, in radio and sonars, in

installations for physical and chemical analysis, in equipment for seismic research, in nuclear experiment technology, etc. Taking into account the requirements for the dynamic range of input signals of information converters leads to the development of special devices for collecting extended range data.

Let's consider the main methods of building data acquisition devices with an extended range.

One way to increase the dynamic range is to use multi-bit linear analog-to-digital converters (ADCs). Considering the form of a wide range of known types of ADCs in extended range data acquisition devices, where mainly multi-bit (m 14) successive approximation ADCs are used, which have an optimal combination of accuracy, speed and hardware costs. As is known [1, p.221], the successive approximation ADC is based on a digital-to-analog converter (DAC), a successive approximation register and a comparator. Restricted to the consideration of the shot and thermal components, the noise voltage has the following relationship for the noise variance at the input of the comparator:

$$D_{\kappa} = \frac{S_{sh}}{4\tau_{ekv}}. \quad (1)$$

At the same time, some parameters have dominant values, while others play a secondary role. Due to the variety of requirements for converters, the forms of efficiency criteria should also be quite diverse. In this case, it is necessary that the criteria have the following properties:

1. Representativeness (the ability to take into account in reasonable proportions all dominant external parameters);
2. Concreteness (the presence of a certain physical meaning);
3. Constructiveness (the possibility of formal use criteria without involving heuristic efficiency estimates);
4. Simplicity (lack of mathematical difficulties, experimental and computational nature in determining specific numerical values of the criterion);

5. Universality (the possibility of applying the criterion for a comprehensive assessment of the effectiveness of information converters of various types and under various conditions);

6. Consistency (the sensitivity of the criterion and the condition for the operation of the device).

The properties of representativeness, constructibility and universality can be provided and reflected in the form of an efficiency criterion in an explicit form. However, from the point of view of the simplicity of the criterion, it is desirable that the minimum number of parameters appear in it. In addition, with a large number of parameters taken into account, it is difficult to construct criteria that have the property of concreteness, i.e. having a clear physical meaning.

In connection with the foregoing, it is advisable to identify the minimum set of external parameters that must and is sufficient to be taken into account when constructing the efficiency criteria for a computational analog-to-digital converter. When solving this problem, we will distinguish between functional and cost external parameters. Next, we determine which parameters from the functional group can be dominant, therefore, they are explicitly included in the criteria for the effectiveness of the ADC.

Reliability can be considered in relation to catastrophic and gradual (degradative) failures. Gradual failures are associated with drifts in the characteristics of the converter, aging of its elements, etc. They do not violate the performance of the computational ADC, but only affect its accuracy. Therefore, if permanent failures are taken into account when assessing the accuracy of the converter, then reliability should be considered only in relation to catastrophic failures.

When constructing a computational ADC based on various ADCs at a certain level of development of circuitry and technology, the reliability of the device, taking into account the use of the same elements, the complexity is determined by a directly proportional value of the cost, that is, based on these considerations, we can accept the cost criterion - in the form of a partial display of reliability and the complexity of

the designed calculation of the ADC. The cost criterion can be displayed.

$$\lambda = \sum_{i=1}^n a_i m_i. \quad (2)$$

One of the most important external parameters is accuracy. It is usually one of the dominant parameters. In this case, in the general case, accuracy is a vector parameter determined by the statistical and dynamic components of the resulting error.

Given that the changes will be made with some discreteness q , the error can be expressed

$$\delta = \frac{q}{2};$$

where q - is the value of the processed function in the interval between two points t_1 and t_2 :

$$q = ft_1 - ft_2 = f\Delta t.$$

From here:

$$\delta = \frac{f\Delta t}{2}.$$

(3)

If we approximate the function f in the interval with Δt a ruler, then formula (3) will take the form:

$$\delta = \frac{\Delta t}{2}. \quad (4)$$

Accuracy is the main characteristic that determines the practicality of this device, an excessive increase in accuracy, as a rule, leads to unnecessary equipment costs or a decrease in performance. In addition, when choosing the type of ADC, the number of bits is first set, which is an indicator of accuracy. Therefore, accuracy is usually taken as the main specification.

As a performance criterion, we can consider information productivity. Information productivity can be represented as the information transfer rate calculated taking into account those and only those errors that significantly affect the

error in the given conditions of its application.

In [2, p. 76] proposed information criteria for evaluating the effectiveness of communication systems - the speed of information transfer and throughput. A number of fundamental results of the theory of optimal information coding are connected with these criteria. At present, the methods of information theory are being used not only for solving communication problems, but also for other problems. In particular, numerous attempts have been made to use the criteria for information transfer rate and throughput.

Taking into account that the developed computational ADC will operate on slowly changing signals, such a criterion as the information transfer rate in determining the collective efficiency criterion can be neglected.

Along with this, it is sometimes convenient to introduce into a set of parameters a system of some generalized parameters that are functions of a group of primary parameters. Of the above parameters, the generalized parameters can be: throughput, combining such primary parameters as accuracy and speed, information transfer rate, etc., cost, which is a function of dimensions, weight, power consumption, ease of use, etc.

In addition, as mentioned above, the cost characterizes in part such criteria as "reliability" and "complexity".

And the throughput criterion combines and partially displays exact, high-speed and informational criteria. Throughput can be characterized as the number of samples per unit of time and this criterion is expressed as [3, p. 194].

$$C = \frac{J}{T_{np}}; \quad (5)$$

where J – is the amount of information processed by the ADC during the time T_{con} .

T_{con} - conversion time.

So, you should choose the two most important parameters, which partially also

characterize other parameters, thanks to which you can choose the optimal structure of the ADC. A similar quality function is used in both works by Shileiko A.V. [4, p.41] to select the optimal structure of specialized digital computing devices. He evaluates the quality of specialized digital computing devices by the ratio of throughput C_i and relative complexity:

$$Q_j = \frac{C_i}{\lambda_i}, \quad (6)$$

relation type criterion (6) often leads to inefficient use of the system's capabilities, this happens for two reasons. First, such criteria ignore both the absolute value of the numerator and the denominator, since a proportional change in the numerator and denominator of the quality function does not affect its value. Secondly, the dependence of the quality index on the parameters included in the denominator of the quality functions becomes essentially non-linear for small values of the denominator. The advantage of the ratio type criterion is that it allows one to easily quantify such important parameters of analyzing devices as accuracy, speed, cost, dimensions, weight, and reliability.

In addition to the "relationship type" criterion, the "weighted sum type" criterion is often used.

$$Q_j = \sum_{i=1}^m \alpha_i g_{ij}; \quad (7)$$

where are α_i - weight coefficients reflecting the degree of possibility of the i -th parameter, and

$$\sum_{i=1}^m \alpha_i = 1; \quad (8)$$

g_{ij} - net quality assessment of the j -th option to the i -th parameter.

The "weighted sum type" test is free from a number of disadvantages of the ratio type test. It is convenient to use it to select the best option from a variety of known devices, according to some specifically chosen parameter. However, it is

difficult, and sometimes impossible, to apply this type of criterion to assess the effectiveness of multi-mode devices, since under different modes the values of the weight coefficients of partial estimates take on different values [5, p.532].

Therefore, to evaluate the effectiveness and select the optimal structure of the computational ADC, the criterion of the "type of relations" is usually used.

To evaluate the effectiveness of non-uniform compensation of a multiplier device, the ratio of throughput to relative complexity is acceptable.

$$Q = \frac{c}{\lambda}; \quad (9)$$

The bandwidth of the computational ADC will be called the value:

$$C = \frac{J}{T_{np.}}; \quad (10)$$

where J – is the amount of information processed by the ADC during the time $T_{con.}$;

Here $T_{con.}$ - is the conversion time.

The relative complexity of the computational ADC is defined as:

$$\lambda = \sum_{i=1}^p a_i n_i; \quad (11)$$

where is n_i - the number of elements of the i -th type;

a_i - weight coefficient corresponding to the elements of this type.

The information content of the analog variable will be quantified in the binary system of information [6, p. 83]. Any function of time whose spectrum is bounded from above by some maximum frequency f_m , according to Kotelnikov's theorem, can be arbitrarily accurately represented by a sequence $2f_m T$ of discrete values, where T – is the considered time interval. Each value of a variable at successive times

$$t_i = \frac{1}{2f_m} i = \sum_i \Delta t_i;$$

(12)

can be represented by level quantization with a digital code. If we denote the value of the discreteness of quantization in x through Δx_m and assume that all values of x are equally probable, then the entropy value for an analog signal can be represented by the formula

$$H_a = -\log_2 \frac{\Delta x_m}{x_m};$$

(13)

where x_m - is the maximum value of the variable x , the value $\frac{\Delta x_m}{x_m}$ is determined mainly by the level of interference that is present at the outputs simultaneously with the useful signal. In some papers, it is called the dynamic range of a variable. For a computational ADC, we define the value of T_{con} as the sum of the times for performing operations by compensated elements for the selected forms of the input and output signals, i.e.

where

$$T_{np} = \sum_{i=1}^m T_{npi}. \quad (14)$$

At the same time, a distinctive feature of the considered specialized analog-to-digital converters, as noted, is multi-mode. To evaluate multi-mode in determining the efficiency of a device, we introduce such characteristics as equivalent relative λ_{ekv} complexity and equivalent Q_{ekv} efficiency. These equivalent characteristics are defined as follows [7]:

$$C_{ekv} = \sum_{j=1}^q C_j;$$

(15)

where C_j - is the information performance of the j -th mode;

q – is the number of operating modes of the computational ADC.

$$\lambda_{ekv} = \sum_{k=1}^r \lambda_k; \quad (16)$$

where λ_k - is the relative complexity of the k -th node of the computing ADC;

r – is the total number of nodes included in this structure of the computational ADC.

$$Q_{ekv} = \frac{C_{ekv}}{\lambda_{ekv}}.$$

If for the mode of a similar task to use simultaneously compensated computational analog-to-digital converters, then their total efficiency Q_{Σ} will be equal to:

$$Q_{\Sigma} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^q C_j}{\sum_{j=1}^q \lambda_j}; \quad (17)$$

where is λ_j - the relative complexity of simultaneously compensated computational analog-to-digital converters operating in the j -th mode.

Comparison of expressions (16) and (17) shows that the efficiency of the integrated device is higher than that of the corresponding complex of homogeneous ones. Indeed, taking the ratio Q_{ekv} and Q_{Σ} we get:

$$\frac{Q_{ekv}}{Q_{\Sigma}} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^q \lambda_j}{\lambda_{ekv}} = \beta.$$

The above ratio is always greater than one, because in a complex device, a number of nodes are common to all or several modes and therefore,

$$\lambda_{ekv} < \sum_{j=1}^q \lambda_j.$$

We call the value β the coefficient of complexing. It characterizes the

frequency of use of the nodes included in the complexed device [8].

As a result, we can conclude that when building a computational ADC, instead of increasing the number of bits of the used ADC, it is desirable to use an amplifier with autoscaling. This will lead to a significant simplification of the circuit, which in turn will lead to an increase in reliability and a decrease in the cost of the overall computer system.

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